

Juridical Analysis of Marine Sand Exploitation by Foreign Vessels in Batam Waters Under the 1982 United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea (UNCLOS)

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ABSTRACT: The exploitation of sea sand by foreign vessels bearing the Singaporean flag in the territorial waters of Batam, Indonesia, not only violates Indonesia's maritime sovereignty under international law, but also breaches the provisions of UNCLOS 1982. In addition to undermining international legal principles, this action also violates key national legal instruments, such as Law No. 32 of 2009 on Environmental Protection and Management, Law No. 32 of 2014 on Marine Affairs, and Government Regulation No. 26 of 2023 on Marine Sediment Management. As a result, it potentially weakens Indonesia's legitimacy and standing both regionally and internationally. This research aims to analyze the nature of violations against international maritime law committed by Singapore-flagged vessels, while also examining the national legal enforcement mechanisms available. Using a normative juridical approach and case study method, the study finds that the activity not only causes legal consequences, but also results in serious environmental damage and threatens the sustainability of Indonesia's marine resources. Therefore, firm and assertive legal action is urgently needed.

KEYWORDS: Marine Sand Exploitation, UNCLOS 1982, Maritime Sovereignty, Environmental Law, Foreign Vessels

I. INTRODUCTION

Indonesia is an archipelagic state whose maritime area is larger than its land territory (Amarrohman, Awaluddin, Yuwono, & Arifin, 2020), which has led to Indonesia being widely recognized as a maritime nation. Its strategic position between the Indian and Pacific Oceans places Indonesia at the heart of global maritime routes, making it a pivotal axis of the world's maritime system. This strategic location, combined with international shipping lanes, provides Indonesia with significant opportunities to develop its marine economic potential (Yudilla, 2021). Indonesia's advantages are not limited to its geographical position alone; the country is also endowed with abundant natural resources. A wide variety of fish species and marine biota inhabit Indonesian waters, contributing to the nation's strong appeal as a marine tourism destination. In addition, Indonesia possesses substantial reserves of oil and natural gas. Its strategic position and abundant natural resources have a significant impact on Indonesia's national development and economic growth (Jaya, 2023). These endowments constitute valuable assets that must be managed and utilized sustainably by all components of Indonesian society.

However, these advantages may simultaneously present challenges and threats. Indonesia's abundant natural resources and its strategic position bordering several countries—such as Malaysia, Vietnam, Thailand, the Philippines, and Singapore—render it vulnerable to security threats and illegal exploitation by foreign actors. Such threats include illegal fishing, piracy, drug smuggling, human trafficking, illegal immigration, espionage, illegal exploitation of oil and gas reserves, and illegal sand mining (Harris, Sudiarso, & Sutanto, 2022). These activities may be conducted by individuals or organized groups from other countries and pose serious threats to Indonesia's sovereignty while causing significant economic losses. One such case occurred in October 2024, involving the illegal exploitation of marine sand by two foreign dredger vessels flying the Singaporean flag in the waters of Batam, which are indisputably part of Indonesia's maritime jurisdiction.

Illegal marine sand exploitation refers to the extraction of seabed sediments, which are commonly used for infrastructure development, business activities, and industrial production (Nashwa, Andiani, Fadlah, & Aliyana, 2024). As an illegal activity, such exploitation is carried out without authorization from the competent Indonesian authorities. Beyond its detrimental environmental impacts, this activity also constitutes a violation of international legal principles, particularly those stipulated in the United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea (UNCLOS) 1982. UNCLOS 1982 represents the embodiment of the international community's aspirations to establish a comprehensive legal framework governing the use and utilization of the seas. Its provisions do not only

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accommodate the interests of coastal states but also address the needs of archipelagic states, landlocked states, and states whose geographical positions are considered disadvantageous.

Broadly speaking, UNCLOS regulates the division of maritime zones into the territorial sea, contiguous zone, Exclusive Economic Zone (EEZ), continental shelf, and the high seas (Ardila & Putra, 2020). It also governs activities carried out by individuals and groups at sea, including the management and utilization of marine resources and seabed sediments. These regulations confer specific rights and obligations upon coastal states. Article 2 of UNCLOS affirms the sovereignty of coastal states over their territorial seas, including the seabed, subsoil, and the airspace above them.

Furthermore, Article 56 of UNCLOS grants coastal states sovereign rights to explore, exploit, conserve, and manage natural resources—both living and non-living—of the waters superjacent to the seabed, as well as of the seabed and its subsoil. In this context, coastal states also possess rights over marine sand within their EEZs, even though the EEZ does not constitute part of the territorial sea. Nevertheless, Article 58 of UNCLOS obliges other states to respect the jurisdiction of the coastal state concerning the management of natural resources and environmental protection (Natalia, 2013).

While coastal states enjoy full sovereignty, Article 17 of UNCLOS grants foreign ships the right of innocent passage through the territorial sea of a coastal state. Article 21 further authorizes coastal states to regulate innocent passage, including provisions related to resource conservation, environmental protection, exploration permits, and customs regulations (Tampi, 2017). Accordingly, under Article 25 of UNCLOS, coastal states are empowered to take necessary steps to prevent passage that is prejudicial to their peace, good order, or security, including initiating legal proceedings against violators (Susetyorini, 2019).

In line with UNCLOS provisions, illegal marine sand exploitation also violates Indonesia's national legal framework. Indonesia ratified UNCLOS 1982 through Law No. 17 of 1985, thereby incorporating its provisions into domestic law. Based on the principle of *pacta sunt servanda*, the provisions of UNCLOS are legally binding and may be enforced under Indonesia's jurisdiction as a coastal state.

Article 4 of Government Regulation No. 36 of 2002 on the Rights and Obligations of Foreign Vessels in Conducting Innocent Passage through Indonesian Waters stipulates that foreign vessels are prohibited from engaging in certain activities during innocent passage. These include acts threatening the sovereignty and territorial integrity of the coastal state, military exercises or weapons testing, espionage, propaganda aimed at undermining national security, launching or landing aircraft or military equipment, and other activities unrelated to continuous and expeditious passage (Zhuo, Rumengan, & Aspan, 2020).

Article 5 of the same regulation further prohibits activities such as loading or unloading goods, currency, or persons in violation of customs, fiscal, immigration, or sanitary laws; fishing activities; research activities; deliberate interference with communication systems; and intentional pollution that causes serious environmental harm (Fajrin, 2012).

Additionally, Articles 36 and 37 of Law No. 32 of 2014 on Marine Affairs prohibit the exploitation of marine resources within Indonesian waters without proper authorization. Articles 66A and 69 of Law No. 45 of 2009 on Fisheries authorize Indonesian authorities to exercise jurisdiction over foreign vessels engaged in illegal activities within Indonesian waters. Article 11 of Government Regulation No. 26 of 2023 on Marine Sediment Management stipulates that only nationally incorporated business entities that have obtained official permits are allowed to utilize marine sediment resources, including marine sand. Furthermore, Article 18 point 12 of Law No. 6 of 2023 concerning the Enactment of Government Regulation in Lieu of Law No. 2 of 2022 on Job Creation confirms that the presence of foreign dredger vessels without proper authorization constitutes a threat to national interests and results in state losses.

Previous studies have primarily focused on issues such as innocent passage rights, maritime policies, marine sediment management, and strategies for safeguarding national sovereignty against foreign threats. For instance, Dewi et al. (2024) emphasize the environmental impacts of marine sediment management without addressing international legal principles. Harris et al. (2022) focus on maritime defense strategies in addressing security threats within Indonesian Archipelagic Sea Lanes but do not examine the legal consequences of natural resource exploitation by foreign vessels. Tampi (2017) analyzes the regulation of innocent passage under UNCLOS 1982 and its implementation, without discussing violations of Indonesian national law. Susetyorini (2019) examines Indonesia's maritime policy from the perspective of UNCLOS 1982 but does not address domestic legal enforcement mechanisms. Therefore, this study seeks to update and integrate these discussions by examining a recent case from 2024 involving illegal marine sand exploitation by Singapore-flagged vessels in the waters of Batam under UNCLOS 1982.

Based on the foregoing background, this study aims to further analyze the forms of violations of international law committed by Singapore-flagged vessels in cases of illegal marine sand exploitation within Indonesian waters, as well as to examine the legal enforcement measures available to the coastal state against foreign vessels that infringe upon its sovereignty within its jurisdiction under national law.

II. FORMULATIONS OF THE PROBLEMS

How do Singapore-flagged vessels violate international law in Indonesian waters under the 1982 United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea (UNCLOS)?

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III. RESEARCH METHOD

This study employs a qualitative research design based on a normative juridical approach to analyze violations of international maritime law committed by Singapore-flagged vessels in Indonesian waters, particularly concerning illegal marine sand exploitation in Batam. The research primarily applies a statutory approach by examining relevant international and national legal instruments governing maritime sovereignty, innocent passage, and marine resource management.

At the international level, the analysis focuses on the United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea (UNCLOS) 1982, especially Articles 2, 17, 19, 25, 56, and 58. At the national level, the study examines Law No. 17 of 1985, Law No. 32 of 2009, Law No. 32 of 2014, Law No. 45 of 2009, Law No. 6 of 2023, Government Regulation No. 26 of 2023, and Government Regulation No. 36 of 2002, which collectively regulate marine jurisdiction, environmental protection, and the conduct of foreign vessels in Indonesian waters.

In addition, a conceptual approach is employed to interpret key principles of international law, including state sovereignty, sovereign rights, territorial integrity, environmental protection, sustainability, and the principle of *pacta sunt servanda*. These concepts are analyzed through doctrinal interpretations and relevant legal scholarship.

The study further incorporates a case study approach, focusing on the October 2024 incident involving illegal marine sand dredging by Singapore-flagged vessels in Batam waters, to contextualize the application of normative legal provisions and assess Indonesia's enforcement authority as a coastal state.

The analysis is conducted through systematic examination of:

1. Primary legal materials: international conventions and Indonesian statutory regulations;
2. Secondary legal materials: peer-reviewed journals, academic literature, and legal commentaries; and
3. Tertiary legal materials: legal dictionaries and authoritative references.

This integrated normative and analytical methodology ensures a focused and comprehensive examination of international law violations and Indonesia's legal enforcement mechanisms in safeguarding maritime sovereignty and marine environmental sustainability.

IV. DISCUSSION

Indonesia ratified the United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea (UNCLOS) 1982 in 1985. This ratification signifies that Indonesia is not merely obliged to respect and acknowledge the provisions of the Convention, but is also legally bound to comply with and implement them. Consequently, all legal instruments within Indonesia, without exception, are required to conform to UNCLOS provisions, including individuals and foreign vessels entering Indonesian waters.

UNCLOS 1982 regulates the legal status and activities of vessels entering the maritime zones of a coastal state, whether such vessels merely transit or anchor within Indonesian waters. Under UNCLOS, coastal states possess sovereign rights that are inviolable, encompassing not only the waters themselves but also the seabed, subsoil, and all natural resources contained therein, as well as the airspace above. Nevertheless, when foreign vessels or aircraft transit Indonesian waters, Indonesia is obliged to guarantee the right of innocent passage, provided that such passage is conducted peacefully and in accordance with the provisions of UNCLOS 1982 governing innocent passage.

Under UNCLOS 1982, the right of innocent passage is regulated in Articles 17 to 32. Article 17 provides that ships of all states, whether coastal or landlocked, enjoy the right of innocent passage through the territorial sea (Doodoh, 2018). However, Article 19 clarifies that passage qualifies as innocent only so long as it is not prejudicial to the peace, good order, or security of the coastal state. Furthermore, such passage must comply with UNCLOS provisions and other applicable principles of international law.

Passage ceases to be considered innocent when conducted in violation of UNCLOS provisions, particularly those stipulated in Article 19 paragraph (2). Prohibited activities include threatening or using force against the sovereignty, territorial integrity, or political independence of the coastal state; conducting military exercises involving weapons; engaging in intelligence-gathering activities; carrying out propaganda detrimental to the coastal state; launching, landing, or operating military aircraft or equipment; loading or unloading goods, currency, or persons in violation of customs, immigration, fiscal, or sanitary laws; causing pollution; fishing; conducting research or surveys; interfering with communication systems; and engaging in other activities unrelated to innocent passage. Warships may also be denied the right of innocent passage if they fail to comply with the coastal state's requirements, including the obligation to display their national flag.

These provisions aim to safeguard security and order within the coastal state's maritime zones while simultaneously ensuring protection for vessels and individuals exercising innocent passage. Although UNCLOS 1982 guarantees these rights, not all international actors adhere to its provisions. A notable violation occurred when Singapore-flagged vessels entered Indonesian waters in the Riau Islands, specifically in Batam, and conducted dredging and stockpiling of marine sand using two dredger vessels, MV YC 6 (8,012 gross tonnage) and MV ZS 9 (8,559 gross tonnage). These activities were carried out illegally, without the requisite documentation or authorization from the coastal state authority, namely Indonesia.

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Such conduct constitutes multiple violations of international maritime law. Article 2 paragraph (1) of UNCLOS 1982 affirms that a coastal state exercises full sovereignty over its territorial sea up to 12 nautical miles from the baseline, including the seabed and all natural resources therein. Marine sand mining directly violates this provision, as marine sand forms part of the coastal state's sovereign natural resources located on the seabed. Additionally, the case violates Article 19 paragraphs (1) and (2)(k) concerning innocent passage, as the activities not only threaten peace and order within Indonesian waters but also bear no direct relation to innocent passage. Consequently, such exploitation is not protected under the right of innocent passage, resulting in the loss of that right and rendering the vessels subject to Indonesian law enforcement jurisdiction.

Importantly, the violation occurred within Indonesia's territorial sea, constituting an infringement of Indonesia's full sovereignty rather than merely a violation of sovereign rights as would be the case in the Exclusive Economic Zone (EEZ). Under Article 56 paragraph (1)(a) and (b) of UNCLOS, Indonesia exercises sovereign rights over natural resources in its EEZ but does not enjoy full sovereignty over the waters themselves. Had the violation occurred in the EEZ, the infringement would be limited to Indonesia's exclusive rights over resource management rather than its territorial sovereignty. Therefore, violations within the territorial sea provide Indonesia with a stronger legal basis to detain, inspect, expel, and prosecute foreign vessels, as such acts directly undermine Indonesia's sovereignty.

Unauthorized marine sand mining also poses serious environmental threats, including coral reef destruction, coastal abrasion, and degradation of marine biodiversity, thereby violating international environmental obligations. Accordingly, UNCLOS 1982 grants coastal states the authority to regulate activities within their territorial seas, particularly regarding innocent passage by foreign vessels. Pursuant to Article 25 of UNCLOS, Indonesia is entitled to implement preventive measures and establish procedures to safeguard its territorial waters, including temporarily suspending innocent passage where necessary to protect national security.

Beyond violating UNCLOS 1982, illegal marine sand mining by Singapore-flagged vessels also contravenes fundamental principles of international law as enshrined in the 1970 United Nations Declaration on Principles of International Law concerning Friendly Relations. All states are obliged to respect the territorial integrity and sovereignty of other states. Illegal marine sand mining within Indonesia's territorial sea constitutes a violation of Indonesia's territorial integrity and sovereignty and may be classified as unlawful non-military intervention under international law.

Accordingly, violations occurring within Indonesian maritime zone such as illegal marine sand mining that damages marine ecosystems and breaches maritime boundaries must be subject to enforcement and sanctions under Indonesian law by the competent authorities, as such actions not only infringe sovereignty but also cause significant state losses (Gerungan, 2016). The dredging and stockpiling of marine sand by Singapore-flagged vessels in the Riau Islands therefore violate not only international legal principles but also Indonesia's national legal framework.

Indonesia has incorporated UNCLOS 1982 into its national legal system through Law No. 17 of 1985. Pursuant to Article 10 paragraph (1) in conjunction with Article 11 paragraphs (1) and (2) of the 1945 Constitution of the Republic of Indonesia, ratified international treaties form an integral part of national law (Sunyowati, 2013). Consequently, violations of international maritime law also constitute violations of Indonesian national law, particularly Law No. 17 of 1985.

The exploitation conducted by foreign vessels lacked environmental permits and approval from Indonesian authorities, frequently resulting in ecosystem disruption, seabed destruction, pollution, and coastal abrasion due to non-compliance with procedural standards (Azuga et al., 2025). Such conduct is expressly prohibited under Article 18 point 12 of Law No. 6 of 2023 concerning the enactment of Government Regulation in Lieu of Law No. 2 of 2022 on Job Creation, which amended Article 35 of Law No. 32 of 2009 on Environmental Protection and Management.

Illegal marine sand mining is further regulated under Government Regulation No. 26 of 2023 on Marine Sediment Management. Article 2 emphasizes that marine sediment exploitation must serve environmental sustainability and safety objectives. The activities conducted by Singapore-flagged vessels were purely commercial in nature, undertaken without official authorization, and thus fundamentally inconsistent with sustainability principles (Naibaho, 2024).

Moreover, Article 22 paragraph (3) of Law No. 32 of 2009 mandates that any business activity with environmental impacts must obtain appropriate permits and comply with all regulatory requirements. This provision applies equally to foreign vessels operating within Indonesian waters, including those engaged in marine sand dredging in Batam. Such unauthorized activities are not merely administrative violations but pose serious risks to marine ecosystems that should be protected.

Accordingly, violations of Article 22 paragraph (3) entail not only administrative liability but also environmental accountability. The Government of Indonesia is therefore entitled to impose stringent sanctions, including criminal penalties, to safeguard sovereignty and ensure the sustainability of marine natural resources. Liability may extend beyond vessel masters to include ship-owning companies and entities issuing operational directives. Furthermore, environmental damage and resource loss enable the coastal state to pursue civil compensation claims.

Based on Article 1365 of the Indonesian Civil Code and Law No. 32 of 2009 on Environmental Protection and Management, both the state and affected communities may initiate legal actions against perpetrators. Indonesia possesses a strong legal foundation to enforce such measures, particularly as UNCLOS 1982 confers full authority upon coastal states to exercise jurisdiction within

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their territorial seas. In practice, enforcement may involve vessel seizure, crew inspection, criminal prosecution, and civil litigation before national courts. Consequently, cooperation between communities and competent authorities is essential to prevent recurring violations and to ensure the continued protection of Indonesia's marine resources.

V. CONCLUSIONS

The illegal marine sand exploitation conducted by Singapore-flagged vessels in Batam waters represents a significant breach of Indonesia's territorial sovereignty and demonstrates a violation of international maritime law, particularly the provisions of UNCLOS 1982. The actions of these vessels went beyond the permissible scope of innocent passage, as they engaged in resource extraction without authorization, directly undermining the sovereign rights of Indonesia as a coastal state.

This incident highlights several key points: first, Indonesia possesses full legal authority over its territorial waters, including the seabed, subsoil, and the natural resources contained within. Foreign vessels are permitted to navigate through territorial waters under the right of innocent passage only if their activities are peaceful, lawful, and do not threaten the security, environmental integrity, or order of the coastal state. The illegal dredging clearly falls outside these permissible activities, nullifying any claim to legal protection under the innocent passage principle.

Second, the exploitation has caused significant environmental damage, including disruption of seabed ecosystems, destruction of coral reefs, sedimentation changes, coastal erosion, and threats to marine biodiversity. Such ecological harm not only undermines environmental sustainability but also jeopardizes the long-term economic potential of Indonesia's marine resources.

Third, the case illustrates gaps in compliance and enforcement, revealing the urgent need for more stringent regulatory oversight, monitoring, and coordinated action between national authorities and maritime law enforcement agencies. Effective control over foreign vessels and resource exploitation is essential to protect sovereignty, maintain order, and ensure sustainable marine resource management.

Fourth, Indonesia has clear legal mechanisms to respond to such violations, including the authority to halt illegal activities, inspect and detain vessels, prosecute responsible parties, and seek compensation for environmental damages. These measures reinforce the principle that coastal states hold the ultimate responsibility for safeguarding their territorial waters and marine resources.

Finally, the case emphasizes the broader strategic importance of maritime governance. It demonstrates that protecting territorial integrity, enforcing international and national laws, and prioritizing environmental sustainability are interconnected imperatives. Strengthened maritime law enforcement, combined with robust legal frameworks and public awareness, is essential to prevent recurrence, preserve ecological balance, and assert Indonesia's position as a sovereign maritime nation.

VI. RECOMMENDATIONS

The findings of this study highlight the urgent need for coordinated, law-based, and environmentally conscious strategies to prevent illegal exploitation of marine resources in Indonesia's territorial waters. Based on the analysis, the following recommendations are proposed:

1. Strengthening Indonesia's Legal and Institutional Framework

Indonesia should enhance the enforcement of national maritime and environmental laws, including Law No. 17 of 1985, Law No. 32 of 2009, Law No. 32 of 2014, Law No. 45 of 2009, Law No. 6 of 2023, and Government Regulation No. 26 of 2023. Specialized investigative and enforcement units should be established to monitor foreign vessels, ensure compliance with licensing and environmental standards, and prosecute violations effectively. Inter-agency coordination among the Indonesian Navy, Maritime Security Agency (Bakamla), Ministry of Maritime Affairs and Fisheries, and Environmental Authorities is essential for rapid intervention and prevention.

2. Enhancing Environmental Protection and Resource Management

Indonesia should implement stricter oversight mechanisms for marine resource exploitation, including real-time monitoring of seabed activities and regular environmental impact assessments. Unauthorized sand dredging, coral reef destruction, and habitat disruption should trigger immediate legal and administrative sanctions. Additionally, developing sustainable marine resource management policies that balance economic use and environmental preservation is critical.

3. Strengthening International Cooperation and Maritime Diplomacy

Indonesia should actively engage with neighboring states and international bodies to prevent illegal cross-border marine exploitation. Bilateral agreements, joint patrols, and intelligence sharing with Singapore and other neighboring countries should be institutionalized to monitor vessel movements, prevent illicit sand extraction, and ensure compliance with UNCLOS 1982.

4. Leveraging Technology for Surveillance and Enforcement

Advanced maritime technologies, including satellite monitoring, automatic identification systems (AIS), and drones, should be utilized to track foreign vessel activities in Indonesia's territorial waters. A centralized database integrating

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environmental, maritime, and legal data can enhance detection of violations, improve enforcement efficiency, and provide evidence for legal proceedings.

5. Promoting Public Awareness and Stakeholder Engagement

Local communities, fishers, and private maritime operators should be educated on the legal, economic, and environmental risks of illegal sand mining. Awareness campaigns and community reporting mechanisms can act as early warning systems and foster public participation in protecting Indonesia's marine sovereignty.

6. Ensuring Legal Accountability and Environmental Compensation

Indonesia should ensure that all violators, including vessel operators and responsible companies, are subject to criminal, administrative, and civil liability. Mechanisms for environmental restoration and compensation must be applied to repair damaged marine ecosystems. Legal proceedings should emphasize deterrence, reinforcing Indonesia's sovereignty and commitment to sustainable resource management.

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